

INTERLOCKING INTERFACE DESIGN IN METAL-CFRP JOINTS USING A MONTE-CARLO SIMULATION APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Experimental single lap joint tests with different interlocking structures in the interface area of carbon fiber reinforced plastic and thermoplastic parts motivates an extended simulative study about the influences of interlocking elements. Due to a lack of information from a small number of experimental test with interlocking elements, conclusions are hard to draw about how to place structures elements in multi material joint interface. A Monte-Carlo simulation approach with a large number of simulations is used to provide more general explanations of the effects and interaction within interlocking interface boundaries. The derived conclusions are a wide distribution of pins, a certain pin density, as well as a staggered positioning of pins to achieve a maximum load capacity and minimum damage initiation in the composite for small displacements.

1 INTRODUCTION

Light weight design is a common method in automotive engineering to face the logistics challenges of a growing globalization and increasing private transportation. Multi-material design is the combination of different materials taking into account their specific properties to meet special requirements. Therefore, not only light materials but the right mixture concerning the application are necessary. Carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) and metals are two common materials in automotive industry and light weight constructions. The challenge of multi-material design is to find proper joints where the common technics like bolts, screws and rivets are unsuitable or adhesives are too time-consuming. For these purposes various joining methods are investigated as it can be seen in [1].

In this contribution the thermoplastic interface between an overmolded metal insert for CFRP-metal joints will be studied. The application is motivated by an innovative metal-CFRP joint which is suitable to mass production as required in automotive industry. Hence, the metal insert is overmolded in an injection molding process which offers the opportunity to produce a fiber-adjusted surface in a time and cost saving way. After injection molding, the insert is placed in a Resin Transfer Molding (RTM)-tool in between of carbon fabric layers where the hybridization by consolidation is conducted intrinsically. The thermoplastic coating does not only provide the ability to generate a fiber-adjusted macroscopic geometry onto a simple stamped metal part further it allows many types of complex surface structures to improve the bonding to the CFRP through mechanical interlocking. The influence of adhesion through mechanical interlocking on metal-CFRP joints is studied for different applications and methods [2]. Additionally, in [3] different polymer surface structures are investigated by single-lap joint (SLJ) experiments. Moreover,

simulative approaches are shown to determine an optimal pin geometry depending on the mode of load.

In this work, the influence and interaction of round pins in the polymer-CFRP interface is examined by SLJ tests. Because of time and expense limitation in experimental test only a specific number of different pin variations can be tested. Hence, conclusions are hard to draw due to the limited number of tests. Those to get a more general idea of the effect of structural load transmitting elements an automated finite element (FE) simulation analysis is implemented. The basic idea is a Monte-Carlo approach which is based on a random choice and statistic. This allows to draw more general inferences from the FE simulation to give an over view of how to place pins.

2 EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

SLJ tests are conducted to examine the CFRP-polymer bonding behavior. Especially single pins and pin pattern are arranged on the polymer surface to determine the interlocking effect. Sample production and repairation is explained as well as the dimensions. Further, experimental tests and the results are presented.

2.1 SPECIMENS

The specimens are made of a thermoplastic polymer component intrinsically consolidated with the CFRP-composites in a RTM process as shown in figure 1, a. The overlapping joint surface is 25x12.5 mm as recommended by DIN EN 1465. The plastic part is a 60x25x8 mm³ beam with a 10° angled overlapping surface (25x12.5 mm²) produced by injection molding from short fiber reinforced Polyphthalamide (PPAGF30) [4]. The beam thickness of 8 mm is caused by different material stiffness between plastic and composite to ensure a symmetric deformation and shear-load in the overlapping zone. Further, the 10° angle of the overlapping surface is determined by parametric simulations to equalize the occurring deformation during the tests as recommended in [5].

The composite consists of two layers woven carbon fabric with 0°-90° orientation [6] with epoxy resin [7]. Preparing the RTM process, the thermoplastic part is placed into the metal mold and two layers of carbon fabric with the size of 25x60 mm² are stacked on to the overlapping surface. The final composite thickness is 0.5 mm. Runners and the cavity in the mold make sure that the fabric gets evenly impregnated and only the overlapping surface of composite part is in contact with resin. To ensure the complete curing the mold is heated up to 75°C for 45 min. before the specimens are ejected.

The load transmitting mesoscale structures has the form of cylindrical pins produced within the injection molding of the thermoplastic part. The pin dimensions are taken from [3] and have a radius of 0.86 mm and a height of 0.5 mm. They are located at the surface of the overlapping area. The single pin is located in the middle of the overlapping area. The other pin patterns with two, three, five and six pins are shown in figure 1, b.

Figure 1: Single lab joint (SLJ) specimen (a), different pin pattern on polymer surface (b)

2.2 TESTING AND RESULTS

SLJ shear tests are performed on a universal testing machine (Shimadzu AG-Xplus) with 2 mm/s displacement velocity. The force until the bonding failure is recorded and different pin patterns are

compared due to their maximum strength and stiffness. The test series consists of five different patterns, each with 6-7 samples. The average results from each pin pattern is displayed in the force-displacement diagram, see Figure 2. On the right side the averaged force-displacement curves of the samples with one to six pins are displayed. On the left side the initial 0.1 mm are shown enlarged. In the first 0.7 mm no critical damage can be observed in the curves. Further, the diagram shows that growing number of pins causes an increase of the transmittable load and larger maximum forces can be resisted before failure occurs. Most times, the failure emerges suddenly and is fatal. That means in single tests the joint fails abruptly and their stiffness drops to very low levels. This causes the zigzag curves in the average diagrams. However, load-displacement curves are plotted from sample geometries with one, two, three, five and six pins. With few exceptions, the average damage occurrence (curve drop) is within the same order. This means that one pin is the weakest bond and 6 pins the strongest. However, it can be seen that the load per pin does not increase proportionally. Comparing the curves with three, five and six pins only small differences in stiffness and strength can be seen. Yet, it should be considered the arrangement of the pins. The way the arrangement influences the bonding behavior is depicted in Figure 2 (zoom, left side). It is a more detailed extraction of the initial curves where the stiffness can be compared. Furthermore, it shows that 2 pins in a row (black line) are stiffer than three pins next to each other (green line).

The influences of pin arrangements are difficult to derive from experimental tests due to the small number of different patterns and the huge effort it takes. This arises the questions, how many pins are necessary and where and how the pins need to be arranged. Simulative investigations of interlocking and load transmitting pins provide further information about stress and damage distributions in the joint interface due to the pin arrangement.

Figure 2: exp. force-displacement curves of different pin pattern (SLJ)

3 SIMULATIONS AND MONTE-CARLO APPROACH

The Monte-Carlo approach is a statistical method which is based on the law of huge numbers. Enough experiments or simulations have to be carried out to draw general conclusions from the distribution. Not all possible combinations are taken into account, but the statistical distribution is expected to result in a uniform dispersion of the results which contain different maxima as well as minima.

To determine the influence of pins, a significant number of different pin patterns has to be simulated. In the Monte-Carlo approach the number of pins in the interface are randomly created and their positions are determined on a checkered pattern by default. The checkered pattern is shown in Figure 7. A Python script is implemented which chooses the pin pattern and creates the FE models. Such an FE simulation study generates a large amount of data. Special data processing and visualization tools are needed to prepare the data for analysis. A framework called *Shiny* [8] which is based on the statistical computing programming language R, is used to analyse the effect

of different pin patterns concerning load transition and the composite damage state to deviate pin pattern influences in CFRP-polymer interface joints.

3.1 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The simulations are carried out with *Abaqus (Simulia)*. An FE model represents the overlapping part of SLJ test specimens (25x12.5x4 mm³). Further, the boundary conditions are defined in such a way that the tensile test is represented and middle symmetry is considered to reduce simulation costs. The model is meshed with an offset mesh from the bonding surface and elements are used that support the implementation of the material model for CFRP from *Helius PFA (Autodesk)* [9]. First, a cohesive layer (COH3D8) with 0.01 mm thickness between polymer and CFRP and additionally two 0.24 mm thick CFRP-layer are created with C3D8R elements. The cohesive layer represents the contact behavior and describes the adhesive behavior between polymer and CFRP. As an assumption, the traction separation as well as stiffness parameter in cohesive elements are reduced to very low levels to disregard adhesive bonding and focus to the effect of interlocking pins at the SLJ. The contact between pin and CFRP is modelled so that it is perfectly bonded as an assumption for small deformations. The composite material behavior is implemented as multi continuum material considering fiber and matrix properties as well as damage behavior with *Helius PFA (Autodesk)*. Two layers oriented in 0°-90°, model the CFRP, compare section 2.1. An overview of the material parameter is shown in Table 1. The polymer is modelled as isotropic with ideal plastic yield point at 93.5 MPa. The composite material model from *Helius* considers the fiber and matrix damage individually and by specific damage criteria. Status variables (SDV) from *Abaqus* are used to print out the damage status in the composite [9]. While different damage status are given in the SDVs, SDV1 gives an overview and sums them up as shown in Table 2.

Materials	Young's modulus (GPa) E ₁₁ /E ₂₂ /E ₃₃	Poisson's ratio ν ₁₂ /ν ₁₃ /ν ₂₃	Shear modulus G ₁₂ /G ₁₃ /G ₂₃ (MPa)	Strength (MPa) R ₁₁₊ /R ₁₁₋ /R ₁₂
Polymer	9.1	0.3	-	-
CFRP	22.97/22.97/2.92	0.04/0.63/0.63	732/637/637	230/-110/24
Cohesive	1x10 ⁻⁹	-	1x10 ⁻⁶	1x10 ⁻⁷

Table 1: Material parameters

SDV1	Discrete composite damage state
1.0	Undamaged matrix, undamaged fiber
1.4	Fill matrix failure/unfailed warp
1.6	Warp failure/unfailed fill
2.0	Matrix failure in warp and fill
2.2	Fill fiber and matrix failure/unfailed warp
2.3	Unfailed fill/warp and matrix failure
2.7	Fill fiber and matrix failure/warp matrix failure
2.8	Fill matrix failure/warp fiber and matrix failure
3.0	Completely failed

Table 2: Discrete composite damage states of *Helius PFA (Autodesk)* [9]

Figure 3: Simulation model of SLJ overlapping area

As shown in Figure 3, the polymer part is fixed (encastre) at one end and a displacement of 0.07 mm is applied to the composite layer at the other side. Further, symmetry is considered at the hinder plane and a pin pattern of polymer (green) in the composite (black) can be seen in Figure 3. The pin arrangement; number and positions is randomly chosen by an automated script which considers certain neighborhood regulations. First, there are 45 spots, considering the symmetry 25 different spots, for the pins. This is better to be seen in Figure 7. But pins are not allowed to stay too close together, which means next to each pin (front, back, beside) the position is omitted. Only diagonal pins are allowed. Figure 3 shows this in an exemplary way. Altogether, 1050 simulations in total with different pin pattern are simulated in this study.

3.2 DATA ANALYSIS AND VISUALISATION

The large number of simulations requires a lot of effort to evaluate the data in order to draw conclusions from the different pin arrangements. The conventional method of viewing and comparing the individual simulations is no longer possible. Therefore, a pre-sorting and the possibility of a clear comparability of the calculations must be created, which allows an evaluation of the study. Advanced visualization techniques are used to address the challenge of big data from simulation and to find proper solutions for the pin arrangement in the interface [10]. First, the overall dimension of the data has to be reduced to fit graphical evaluation tools like plots as it is an important step in visual analytics [11]. In detail we extracted information like transmitted load, the number of elements for specific damage states, as well as information about the time step, number of pins.

In the next step, the *Shiny* framework is used to build up a tailored tool for processing the beforehand extracted data. The design follows the mantra of Keim et al. [12]: “Analyse first, zoom/filter, analyze further, details on demand” to support both, overview and detailed visual representation. This tool is capable of loading data; creating new data columns as it might be from greater interest to show for example a relation using simple mathematical operations between two data columns. Given a tab-based design like modern browsers it is possible to look at only one simulation or to compare multiple simulations at once for equal time steps. For evaluation purposes the observation concentrates on the multiple simulation view. For this view the user is able to select all equal time steps, showing the data in plots with customizable parameter axis, so that the user has maximum control over observing the data. More than one plot was used, a linked and multi view design as discussed by Roberts [13] to support interactive selection and brushing in plots resulting in a synchronized marking in every plot is included. In order to also support an in-depth analysis of dense data points, an additionally zooming option was implemented. This is especially useful for data points with same number of pins. By selecting a data point, the user could also see

the related pin patterns of the simulation. Furthermore, a context was included and linked to *Abaqus* for a specific comparison of two selected data points in terms of a colored surface for von-Mises stress and discrete damage state of composite material (SDV1). Pictures generated by the tool are given in Figure 5.

In Figure 4, an exemplary diagram is shown where three data point are selected and the related pin distributions are added to the view. The transmitted force is plotted over the number of pins. With the increasing number of pins, transmitted load rises too. It can be seen for each number of pins the results of different pin patterns vary in a certain range. This range is very small for a few pins due to the fact that the position of a lonely pin does not have a huge impact to the bonding. The range also decreases with larger numbers of pins. This is because of limited space and the pin restriction to certain positions, means, the more pins the less variety in positions are possible.

Figure 4: load-pin-correlation of 1050 simulations

3.3 SIMULATION RESULTS

By taking a closer look to the results different fields are analyzed to address the remaining questions of how many pins and where to place them. First, this includes the load transmissions values. Second, the damage status will be examined to derive the effects of pin arrangements towards to damage developments.

The clearest and most important result from the Monte-Carlo simulation is the converging maximum transferable load of the pin arrangements in Figure 4. Already 14 pins can transfer a load of 412 N in the model with a displacement of 0.07 mm. This is within the range of the diverging maximum with a percentage difference of less than 1.5 % (see Table 3). Especially interesting is that the best combination with 14 pins is as strong as the best combination with 16 pins, which means no further improvement with more pins here. For all pin combinations before, the general trend of the best simulations is that a higher number of pins transfers more load. This is no longer the overall case with 14 pins and more. Beside the transmitted load, table 3 contains the deviation to the optimum (21 pins) and three different damage variables derived from the status variable SDV1 that gives an overview about the damage in the composite.

Pins	SDV1sum	SDV1avg	SDV1amount	Transmitted load [N]	Deviation to optimum [%]
1	696	1.82	382.00	72.37	83.00
2	1083	1.79	606.00	133.76	68.30
3	1242	1.72	723.00	195.01	53.63
4	1225	1.65	744.00	255.31	39.19

5	1139	1.62	704.00	299.66	28.57
6	1015	1.59	637.00	321.76	23.28
7	1029	1.60	643.00	345.37	17.63
8	787	1.63	484.00	362.62	13.50
9	838	1.62	516.00	374.86	10.57
10	763	1.61	475.00	382.80	8.67
11	454	1.57	289.00	392.38	6.37
12	667	1.61	414.00	396.06	5.49
13	434	1.55	280.00	407.67	2.71
14	365	1.57	233.00	412.76	1.50
15	349	1.56	224.00	414.05	1.19
16	546	1.64	332.00	412.75	1.50
17	497	1.63	305.00	413.52	1.31
18	436	1.65	264.00	417.37	0.39
19	419	1.65	254.00	415.90	0.74
20	421	1.64	256.00	416.15	0.68
21	390	1.64	238.00	419.00	0.00
22	413	1.64	251.00	414.76	1.02
23	385	1.65	234.00	417.65	0.32

Table 3: simulation with highest load transfer for each pin number

Pins	SDV1sum	SDV1avg	SDV1amount	Transmitted load [N]	Deviation to optimum [%]
16	546	1.64	332.00	412.75	1.49
14	365	1.57	233.00	412.76	1.49
17	497	1.63	305.00	413.52	1.31
15	349	1.56	224.00	414.05	1.18
22	413	1.64	251.00	414.76	1.01
19	419	1.65	254.00	415.90	0.74
20	421	1.64	256.00	416.15	0.68
18	436	1.65	264.00	417.37	0.39
23	385	1.65	234.00	417.65	0.32
21	390	1.64	238.00	419.00	0.00

Table 4: best simulations 14-23 in row

Table 4 shows the best combinations of pin numbers 14 to 23 in increasing load transferability. Looking at the order of table 4, it can be seen that the best possible combination has 21 pins and carries 419 N. Thus, this simulation is stronger than the best 23 pin simulation, which is the maximum number of pins and it transmits 417 N.

Even though it is considered that the 1050 randomly selected simulations of the Monte-Carlo approach are only a fraction of all possible combinations, it is unlikely to find a combination with significant deviation. In addition, there is only one possible combination with 23 pins due to neighborhood regulations and it transfers already less load than the optimum with 21 pins.

The consideration of the strongest 50 arrangements of all 1050 simulations shows many combinations with 18 pins. This shows that many different combinations are possible and a large number of arrangements is particularly favorable for load transfer. A total of 85 different combinations with 18 pins were calculated, where the maximum difference from highest to lowest load transmission is 24 N (417 N-393 N). In Figure 4 it can be seen that the number of simulations increases with the number of pins and thus also the scattering range of the results obtained, which decreases again from 14 pins onwards. Maximum load transfer differences can be seen, for example, with 5 or 8 pins where the scattering is over 100 N with 54 simulations each. The small

difference with 18 pins shows that an area ratio of 6.5 (total area/pin area), which means an area coverage with pins of about 13% of the total area, seems particularly favorable for the connection in this study

The comparison of the 54 simulated arrangements with 8 pins shows a large range of the pin distribution and transmitted loads, which vary from 258 N to 362 N. The difference in the results of more than 100 N can be explained by the distribution of the pins and will be examined in more detail. With the same number of pins distributed over the area, the load transmission fluctuates strongly despite the same pin density of 5.95% (related to the entire connection area). The weakest three variants with 8 pins carry significantly lower loads and deviate greatly from the other simulations. While the difference of the next better simulations in the main cluster is about 2-6 N, the weakest three variants each have differences of about 15 N to each other (see Figure 4: 258 N, 273 N, 287 N). This happens because of the fact that in the majority of simulations the pin arrangement is similar or varies only slightly. In the last three samples, on the other hand, particularly unfavorable configurations of the arrangement occur. This is the case with the weakest variant, as it has a very dense pin arrangement in a diamond-like order, see Figure 5. In addition, only a small part of the connection area is covered with pins, which means that a large part of the area is unused for connection purposes.

The comparison with only four pins in a diamond-like pattern shows that only 33 N load transfer is achieved by double the number of pins due to the high local density of the pins. However, it should be noted that the effective area covered with pins (area enclosed by the outer pins, see diamond) does not increase. Further, it should be noted that even if the increase of transferred load is quite small, the higher pin amount with offset arrangement in the diamond-like order decreases the damage development in the composite (average damage value). From this, it can be seen that a denser pin arrangement enables the damage to develop and the load to increase. The diamond-shape does not only have a particularly dense arrangement but is also offset one behind the other in the tensile direction. This leads to less damage. In Figure 5 the eight pin pattern only shows damage at the two outer pins whereas the four pin pattern shows damaged at all four pins and the average damage status is slightly higher.

Figure 5: v. Mises stress and average damage status of four and eight pin diamond pattern

Figure 6: Alternating pin arrangement of eight pins

The peak performance at eight pins is provided by the arrangement which has five pins in the front row and three in the back row, with the central pins in line one behind the other. Based on von Mises stress it can be seen that less stress occurs at the rear middle pin and thus less load is transmitted. The questions arise how important an alternating arrangement is and what influence the arrangement of the pins has on the front and back. This can be observed in the following comparison of five pins with maximum wide and even offset distribution. Simulations with five pins, each located in its own column, are considered as shown in Figure 7. The alternating arrangement of five pins is possible in two ways. Either, three pins at the front and two at the back or the inverted arrangement can be selected. Between these two arrangements there is a small difference in the load transfer in the simulations. The five pins next to each other in a row are the reference. This arrangement is able to transmit 290.83 N. Even small alternating displacements show a strengthening effect. While a spacing of 4 mm between each pin supports 4 to 6 N more compared to the line-like setup, a spacing of 8 mm increases this even further to approximately 9 to 10 N. The best performance shows the arrangement with two pins in front and three at the back. This simulation transmits 299.66 N. The difference can be explained by the unsymmetrical setup of the model in load direction.

Figure 7: alternating pin arrangement of five pins

Figure 8: damage per pin in SDV1sum-pin diagram

In order to evaluate the damage development in the composite three status variables are derived as listed in Tables 3 and 4: Sum of the damage status variables SVD1, average value of SVD1 and number of damaged elements. Figure 8 shows the sum of SDV1 of all damaged elements, which allows a statement about how intense damage distribution is. The consideration of the averaged damage or the smallest damage per pin number shows an initially increasing curve with maximum at four pins and then again decreasing values. The further curve converges approximately against a number of about 200 damaged elements. In the Figures 5, 6 and 9, von Mises stress as well as the damage status is depicted in contour plots. The highest stress concentrations can be found at the outer edges of the pins. In addition, the damage status is highest at these edges in all shown examples. The simulation with the least damage and the fewest pins has 9 pins. The reason for the low damage is to be found in the arrow-shaped arrangement of the pins as depicted in Figure 9. The position of pins is staggered one behind the other.

Figure 9: arrow-shaped nine pin pattern

4 CONCLUSION

First conclusions concerning the pin influence can be drawn from the SLJ tests. The results from experimental test with SLJ of CFRP composite and polymer show an increase in load capacity from one to six pins. Due to excessive workload and huge deviations only small number of tests can be conducted which leads to a lack of information to interpret the influence of pins and their arrangement to each other in concerns of increasing the load capacity. Hence, simulations with a Monte-Carlo approach has been conducted to gain more knowledge about pin patterns influence.

Based on the Monte-Carlo simulation it can be concluded that the maximum stiffness and load transmission due to interlocking by pins converge against a maximum level. For the specified boundaries in this SLJ application the values of 14 pins reach a maximum of transmitted load within a deviation of less than 1.5%. 14 round pins correspond to a pin density of 10.4% on the connection area or an area ratio of the connection area to the pin area of 9.6. Using the simulations as a basis, concrete arrangements for pin structures can be given or boundary conditions for randomly distributed pins can be derived. If pins are randomly distributed on the surface 13.4% of the surface should be covered by pins. This recommendation results of the fact that despite a large number of different arrangements, the results of 18 pins show the smallest variation. It must be ensured that the neighborhood regulation is regarded so that pins are not too close to each other.

An unsurprising finding is that an even and wide distribution of the pins is important for a good interlocking load transfer. The best performing pin patterns are always widespread over the bonding area. The complementary example is the diamond-shaped pattern where pins are very close to each other and only small forces are transferred.

With the intention to distribute pins in a structured way, they should be arranged staggered behind each other. This is shown in different examples. The staggered pattern ensures that all pins carry the maximum of load while pins close behind another do not use their total potential. Beside the load capacity an alternating/staggered arrangement next to and behind each other is important to minimize damage development. Especially with pins lying one behind the other, crack propagation is increased. In contrast, pin structures arranged staggered one behind the other are particularly low in damage.

5 OUTLOOK

From the Monte-Carlo simulation approach published in the article and the gained insights, further simulative considerations with extended simulation models and other boundary conditions can be set up and allow a freer positioning of the pins. Further, the pin geometry needs to be examined to gain an optimal shape under certain load cases. Experimental and simulative investigations on the influence of different stiffness pairs on the materials can also be carried out, to prove the transferability to other material combination. The considerations of progressive damage and detachment in the case of larger deformations as well as the relationships between adhesive and interlocking connections must be further researched and understood.

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